

D6.2: Report on an integrated business plan

Sven Fahrner, Roland Pieruschka | 30 June 2021

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Authors (Partner)				
Responsible author	Name	Sven Fahrner	Email	s.fahrner@fz-juelich.de
		Roland Pieruschka		r.pieruschka@fz-juelich.de

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Documents used in the preparation of this deliverable:

- Preparatory documents of the 4th EMPHASIS Ministry Meeting (confidential)
- Minutes of the 4th EMPHASIS Ministry Meeting (confidential)
- Preparatory documents of the 3rd EMPHASIS Ministry Meeting (confidential)
- Minutes of the 3rd EMPHASIS Ministry Meeting (confidential)
- Preparatory documents of the 1st EMPHASIS Interim General Assembly Meeting (confidential)
- Minutes of the 1st EMPHASIS Interim General Assembly Meeting (confidential)
- Preparatory documents of the 2nd EMPHASIS Interim General Assembly Meeting (confidential)
- Minutes of the 2nd EMPHASIS Interim General Assembly Meeting (confidential)
- Preparatory documents of the 3rd EMPHASIS Interim General Assembly Meeting (confidential)
- Minutes of the 3rd EMPHASIS Interim General Assembly Meeting (confidential)
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D1.5: Third-year General Assembly
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D1.6: Fourth-year General Assembly
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D2.1: Criteria list for infrastructure
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D2.2: Criteria list for user demand
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D2.3: Mapping: list of existing/upcoming infrastructures
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D2.4: Gap analysis

- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D2.5: Report on current and future user demands
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D2.6: Criteria for life cycle assessment
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D2.7: Operational cost models
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D3.1: Communication strategy
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D3.2: Mapping of training activities
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D3.3: Report on user orientation towards services
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D3.4: Trend document
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D4.1: Map of data practices
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D4.2: Strategy: Data Management Plan
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D4.3: Link with other information systems
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D4.4: Analysis of imaging approaches
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D4.5: Data policy rules
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D5.1: Scenarios for governance structures
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D5.2: Rules for the representation of national infrastructures
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D5.3: Options to form a legal entity
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D5.4: Governance framework including roles and responsibilities for the implementation phase
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D5.5: Report on operations for selection of host country for EMPHASIS central hub and potential services
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D5.6: Governance and Statutes for the EMPHASIS Operational Phase
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D6.1: Report on financial and funding framework, including criteria of participation to EMPHASIS
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D6.3: Report on services tested and potential KPIs

1. Executive Summary

Scope of this deliverable

This deliverable presents the EMPHASIS business plan as key document resulting from the EMPHASIS-Prep project. It addresses all strategic aspects of relevance for implementing EMPHASIS as a pan-European service organisation, including the:

- Business model,
- User and service provision strategy,
- Legal and governance issues,
- Cost model, and
- Implementation work plan.

Main results of this deliverable

To the time of the finalisation of this deliverable, EMPHASIS has entered a crucial step in its life cycle. It has started conceptualising its Implementation Phase already 2018 and worked towards establishing an interim governance enabling high-level decision making since then. Accordingly, it has established its Interim General Assembly as its highest governing during the Implementation Phase which has already taking key decisions towards the end of the preparatory project in June 2021. These (among others) comprise a decision on the business model, the user strategy, the content and financial support for the Implementation Phase as described in the implementation work plan, and on the long-term legal framework (=ERIC). Other major decisions (on the cost model and the statutory seat country) are foreseen to be taken in the second half of 2021.

Thus, this deliverable can present details on the strategic decisions already taken, while aspects still being negotiated within the Interim General Assembly are described on a coarser level in line with the current negotiation situation.

2. Core aspects of the business model

Vision

By integrating the European plant phenotyping infrastructures, EMPHASIS will develop plant phenotyping infrastructure and enable access to plant phenotyping facilities, data, resources and other services to advance basic and applied plant science required to enhance breeding of sustainable crops with higher quantity and quality of yield as a cornerstone for food security and European bio-economy in times of changing climate.

Context - scientific challenges and gaps addressed

Several complex and interconnected megatrends raise the requirement for enhancements in the quantity and quality of sustainable crop production contributing to sustainable bioeconomy in Europe and beyond: increased demand for high-quality food and feed production, demand for increase of green energy production, demand for natural resource, while there is no additional arable land and climate change poses additional pressure. Plant Breeding is responsible for about 50% of crop productivity increase over the last century while the remainder of the yield increase comes from better crop management (e.g., fertilization, irrigation, weeding) and further effort specifically towards breeding is needed to address future challenges (FAO 2020¹). In this context plant phenotyping in combination with genomics will providing new foundations for crop-breeding systems².

Creating new plant varieties in breeding is a long-term process, which may take a decade or more. The major bottleneck in speeding up this process is understanding the relation of genetic information (GENOTYPE) with environmental factors (ENVIRONMENT) determining the (PHENOTYPE) being the most important to breeders, agriculturists, food producers and biologists: phenotypic characteristics such as yield, quality, resilience to abiotic and biotic stress etc. (Figure 1).

¹ <http://www.fao.org/3/a-at913e.pdf>

² <https://www.nature.com/articles/nature22011>

Figure 1: The interaction between the GENOTYPE and the ENVIRONMENT determines the PHENOTYPE.

Rapid technological developments within the last decades specifically with respect to sequencing technologies have resulted in abundance of genetic data while the essential information on the phenotype is lagging behind. This so-called “phenotyping bottleneck” requires development and access to state-of-the-art plant phenotyping infrastructure that will enable novel understanding of plant processes that can be transferred into application, open science leading to innovations in the fields of imaging technologies, robotics, automatization, data management.

EMPHASIS will integrate these developments in Europe leading to investment in highly demanded infrastructure, enabling access to the facilities, data, resources and other services for European scientists. This will further strengthen Europeans leading role in plant phenotyping by fostering excellent science and the transfer of this knowledge into application. For example, since 2000, yields across all major arable crops cultivated in Europe have already increased by approximately 16 % as a result of genetic crop improvement. With every percentage of growth creating additional social welfare by about 500 million €, innovation in plant breeding has generated an additional 8 billion €³.

Lead-up to EMPHASIS infrastructure

The quantitative assessment of plant structure and function has been addressed by plant biologists for decades, yet usually often by using manual or invasive i.e. destructive methods. Application of non-invasive, image based technology for plant phenotyping started with the model plant *Arabidopsis* with a sufficient number of genotypes providing the opportunity to associate traits to the genetic make-up of a plant. Further development of new technology and automation has led to the establishment of first companies providing plant phenotyping equipment such as Lemnatec or

³ http://www.plantetp.org/system/files/publications/files/hffa_research_paper_plant_breeding_eu.pdf

PSI as well as plant phenotyping projects to address Arabidopsis phenotyping in FP6 AGRON-OMICS⁴, develop technology for phenotyping of different crops and plant organs in FP7 projects SPICY⁵, EURoot⁶, DROPS⁷. Those projects indicated an increasing demand for plant phenotyping technology which has led to the FP7 I3 project EPPN⁸ (2012-2015 European Plant Phenotyping Network) a starting community project that provided transnational access to 23 experimental plant phenotyping installations at 7 different institutions, in 5 countries across Europe. The project resulted in 66 transnational access experiments, >50 peer reviewed publications. Based on the success of EPPN and the increasing demand for plant phenotyping a H2020 advanced community I3 project EPPN2020⁹ was approved (2017-2021) providing the opportunity for >150 potential plant phenotyping transnational access experiments and integrating 31 key plant phenotyping installations in 11 European countries. Furthermore, the COST Action¹⁰ “The quest for tolerant varieties - Phenotyping at plant and cellular level” started in 2011 and created a network and very intense interaction of European scientists with expertise on phenotyping, various omics areas plant physiology important to understand tolerance.

In parallel there was a substantial investment in establishing national plant phenotyping infrastructure for instance the German Plant Phenotyping Network (DPPN, 2012-2018: 35 Mil €), The French Plant Phenotyping Network (FPPN, 2013-2020: 30 Mil €), UK with BBSRC and ERC grants (25 Mil €), Belgium (2.5 Mil €) representing many of the installations in EPPN and EPPN2020. The current investment in plant phenotyping infrastructure is estimated to reach 200 Mil € (own estimates based on the mapping activities).

All these concerted activities have led to a well-established community, ready to take the next step to a pan-European plant phenotyping infrastructure in the form of EMPHASIS resulting in a successful application and entry onto the 2016 ESRI Roadmap as the only new infrastructure added at that time as part of the Health and Food domain. Since entering the ESRI roadmap, EMPHASIS could already support (1) the acquisition of funding for plant phenotyping infrastructure via national / regional infrastructure funding mechanisms (NordPlant in Scandinavia, NPEC in The Netherlands,

⁴ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/85221/en>

⁵ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/211347/reporting>

⁶ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/289300/reporting>

⁷ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/244374>

⁸ <https://www.plant-phenotyping-network.eu/>

⁹ <https://eppn2020.plant-phenotyping.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://www.cost.eu/actions/FA1306>

NaPPI in Finland) further proposals were submitted recently in Czech Republic and Norway, (2) proposals for the integration of plant phenotyping infrastructure on national infrastructure roadmaps (Estonia, Poland, Austria), (3) the establishment of national plant phenotyping initiatives (Ireland, Italy, Austria, Czech Republic, Cyprus) (4) the initiation of national plant phenotyping initiatives (Bulgaria, Denmark, Israel, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland).

Built on these activities, EMPHASIS will integrate the European plant phenotyping infrastructure and address all the scales using novel methods and technology under controlled and field conditions, which will be complemented by modelling and a European information systems. EMPHASIS has thus the potential to become the nucleus for the quantum leap in understanding plant environment interaction and translation of this knowledge into breeding needed to address future grand challenges.

Strategic aims of EMPHASIS

The key objectives of EMPHASIS focus around the integration of the pan-European plant phenotyping infrastructure to:

1. develop an integrated pan-European network of instrumented phenotyping platforms able to test genotypes using current and future agro-climatic scenarios, thereby providing community access to facilities under controlled and field conditions;
2. link data acquisition to a European-level information system, data and computational services and to state-of-the art crop models to simulate plants and crops in current and future climates
3. develop, evaluate and disseminate novel technologies, thereby providing new opportunities to European SMEs involved in phenotyping and precision agriculture.

The EMPHASIS Business Model Canvas (Figure 2) summarizes the approach in more detail.

<p><u>Key Partners</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Commission. • National funding agencies. • National plant phenotyping infrastructures and communities. • ESFRI Forum 	<p><u>Key Activities</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific excellence driven access to phenotyping facilities • Infrastructure quality • Enabling FAIR access to plant related data (environment & phenotype) fostering Open Innovation. • Community building & expert advice • Innovation • Support and Coordination • Training & education 	<p><u>Value Propositions</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Global leadership of European plant phenotyping • Facilitating innovation • Knowledge transfer and education • Decision-making support for policy makers towards food security in changing climate conditions • FAIR phenotyping data contributing to digital life sciences in Europe • Societal progress towards a sustainable bioeconomy 	<p><u>Stakeholder engagement</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication strategy with a diversity of targeted instruments. • Demand assessment of diverse user groups. • Annual stakeholder meetings. • Reports and recommendations. • Expert opinion /consulting. 	<p><u>Beneficiaries</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Investors in plant phenotyping infrastructure in Europe (national ministries, funding organisations, EC). • Operators of Plant Phenotyping Infrastructures in Europe. • Academic users of plant phenotyping infrastructure. • Industry users of phenotyping infrastructure, especially in the field of breeding and technology development. • Civil society in Europe.
	<p><u>Key Resources</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Funding for Functional Units 		<p><u>Channels</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online catalogue of Services • Online data and knowledge repository 	
<p><u>Cost Structure</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Functional Units operation 		<p><u>Funding structure</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual full member monetary and in-kind contributions • Host countries contributions • National and regional infrastructure funds • EU grants (Horizon Europe) • Service provision fees (for industry users) • Industry partnership contributions 		

Figure 2: EMPHASIS business model canvas (last update: June 2021).

3. Core aspects of user and service provision strategy

User community

EMPHASIS addresses a very wide and diverse and multidisciplinary user community that includes the plant science, agriculture and food sector providing 30 Mil jobs in Europe, adding 3.5% of the gross-added value with 50.000 scientists in public and 13.000 researchers in industry¹¹. This diverse community addresses a various questions related to the plant-environment relation from basic understanding to application. Therefore, the user community has been evaluated based on thorough exchange in the Preparatory Phase project EMPHASIS-PREP (Table 1) and the service portfolio was developed to specifically address the needs of the users and maximizing the socio-economic impact.

Table 1: EMPHASIS user groups.

User Group	Demand for
I. Scientists and managerial staff operating the infrastructure	- EMPHASIS services related to management of the infrastructure and quality management incl. experimental and data standards - high quality standards at phenotyping installations are the basis for excellent science and data reusability.
II. User from academia and industry interested in access to EMPHASIS services	- access to the EMPHASIS installations, data, resources and services - understanding the plant environment interaction and the translation of this understanding into application e.g. in breeding.
III. Users developing technology	- access to EMPHASIS installations and expertise to develop and validate new technology under realistic scenarios
IV. Funders and Policy makers	- recommendations based on recurrent analysis of the plant phenotyping infrastructure and landscape in Europe; an important tool for the development a cutting-edge research strategy agenda

¹¹ http://www.plantetp.org/system/files/publications/files/plant_etp_summaryactionplans.pdf

User Group	Demand for
	that will further advance the leading role in Europe in agricultural and plant sciences.
V. Public	- dialog open discussion on the important role for sustainable food security and further advancement in plant phenotyping and breeding.

Further details on the EMPHASIS user community and the demands can be found in:

- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D2.2: Criteria list for user demand,
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D2.5: Report on current and future user demands,
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D3.1: Communication strategy,
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D3.2: Mapping of training activities,
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D3.3: Report on user orientation towards services,
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D3.4: Trend document.

Generating benefits through EMPHASIS Functional Units

EMPHASIS will provide services that are driven by user demand with the overarching goal to develop an agile structure for high quality service provision that will allow maintaining and strengthening the Europe’s leading role in plant phenotyping as a basis for further advancement in basic and applied plant sciences. The services will be continuously evaluated to provide high quality of cost effective benefit to the user community and to identify and address new upcoming needs and demands of the community. Additionally, EMPHASIS will be engaged in close interaction with other plant phenotyping activities beyond Europe such as IPPN, Wheat Initiative, CGIAR etc. as well as other ESFRI projects (within the ENVRI-Community¹², within Life Science-RIs¹³, and as partner in RI-VIS¹⁴, EOSC-Life¹⁵) to use and implement the available synergies. All services will be accessible via

¹² <https://envri.eu/>

¹³ <https://lifescience-ri.eu/home.html>

¹⁴ <https://ri-vis.eu/network/rivis/home>

¹⁵ <https://www.eosc-life.eu/>

an online Catalogue of Services as one-stop-shop for its users which will also be accessible via catalogue of services of partnering RIs.

The EMPHASIS services are grouped in Functional Units (Table 2) targeting well-defined user demand in specific areas based on the evaluation of the current status of plant phenotyping infrastructure and the user community in Europe. Each of these units contains a list of very specific services for different stakeholders and will be continuously evaluated to provide demanded services according to a unit-specific set of Key Performance Indicators.

Table 2: EMPHASIS Functional Units (=service providers). Please note, the list of services is not complete and will be further and continuously developed to address the dynamic user demand.

Functional Unit	Specific services	User Groups as in Table 1	Access mode
I. User access	a) User access to infrastructure under controlled environment b) User access to field installations including intense field and network of field sites c) User access to modelling services d) Facilitating R&D user projects utilizing plant phenotyping infrastructure	I) Scientists and managerial staff II) Users from academia and industry	On-demand, on-site access for academia based on a competitive application process for industry based on fee for access
II. Infrastructure quality	a) Harmonising plant phenotyping standards b) Technological capacity development based on common standards c) Staff exchange programmes to foster implementation of common standards	I) Scientists and managerial staff III) Users developing technology	Close interaction within the EMPHASIS Functional Units and service, specifically, access providers

Functional Unit	Specific services	User Groups as in Table 1	Access mode
	d) Facilitating R&D user projects addressing quality management		
III. Data and Computational Services	a) Coordination of data management in EMPHASIS b) Innovate data management within the pan-European Information system c) Enable user access to data d) Staff exchange programmes e.g. to implement data standards e) Facilitating R&D projects addressing data management	I) Scientists and managerial staff II) Users from academia and industry III) Users developing technology	Close interaction within the EMPHASIS infrastructure and Functional Units, access to data based on the data policy
IV. Innovation	a) Validation of technology in realistic scenarios at EMPHASIS infrastructure b) Consulting on innovation within the plant phenotyping landscape c) Legal support for innovation d) Private public partnership for technology development e) Technology dissemination e) Facilitating innovation projects	I) Scientists and managerial staff II) Users from academia and industry III) Users developing technology	(1) services for academia (2) on-demand fee for service for technology validation, consulting, legal support from industry
V. Communication	a) User engagement (websites, workshops conferences) b) Interaction with strategic partners, e.g. ESFRI projects c) Dissemination of EMPHASIS results	I) Scientists and managerial staff II) Users from academia and industry	(1) free service (2) service based on event registration

Functional Unit	Specific services	User Groups as in Table 1	Access mode
	d) Engagement of stakeholders from academia, industry policy, funders and public	III) Users developing technology IV) Funders and Policy makers V) Public	
VI. Training	a) Training of users b) Training of local infrastructure managers c) Modular training material for different groups d) Raising funding for training and education e) Mentoring programme	I) Scientists and managerial staff II) Users from academia and industry III) Users developing technology	Service to the academic user community, fee-based access for industry users
VII. Support and Coordination	a) Supports decision making of EMPHASIS General Assembly b) Coordinates all processes at the interface between different governance parts and their environment c) administrative support d) legal support c) Expert advice	I) Scientists and managerial staff II) Users from academia and industry III) Users developing technology IV) Funders and Policy makers	Free service

All Functional Units will closely collaborate with national infrastructures and local facilities in EMPHASIS member countries (Table 3) for efficient service provision. From a legal perspective, the cooperation will be defined in service level agreements between the EMPHASIS legal entity and each collaborating national infrastructure and local facility.

Table 3: Levels involved in service provision .

1. Functional Unit:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible for the pan-European service provision strategy • Pan-European focus of activities • Part of EMPHASIS legal entity • Integrating / interconnecting national and local infrastructure
2. National Infrastructure:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible for the development of the national community • Integration of services within a country • Coordinating national activities, national focus • Not part of EMPHASIS legal entity (service level agreements define the responsibilities of both the national infrastructure and the EMPHASIS legal entity)
3. Local Infrastructure/Installation:
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible for service provision on facility level e.g. access to installations, data etc. • Not part of the EMPHASIS legal entity (linked to National Infrastructure through service agreements)

The concrete function, responsibility and contribution of each level will be specific for each service and has to be defined a priori as a service operation within the strategy of each Functional Unit, which will be evaluated and decided on by the General Assembly in the course of the overall EMPHASIS strategy development (preferably each five years). Close interaction between the Functional Units and all levels will ensure excellence science at the installation level and a pan European synergistic utilisation of the results across Europe. A continuous re-development of services based on user demand and the key performance indicators that will be developed for every single service is an integral part of the strategy and may follow the concept outlined in Figure 3.

Figure 3: A concept for service re-development towards improved benefit generation (figure adapted from Elisabetta Marafioti, University Milano-Bicocca, EMMRI¹⁶ & RiTrain¹⁷)

Further details on the EMPHASIS service provision can be found in:

- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D2.1: Criteria list for infrastructure,
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D2.6: Criteria for life cycle assessment,
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D4.1: Map of data practices,
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D4.2: Strategy: Data Management Plan,
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D4.3: Link with other information systems,
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D4.4: Analysis of imaging approaches,
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D4.5: Data policy rules.

4. Core aspects of legal framework and governance

Governance supporting implementation

EMPHASIS started conceptualising its implementation already in 2018 well in advance to the end of the EMPHASIS-Prep project in June 2021. The EMPHASIS Implementation Phase:

- is intended to be easy to set up and not too time consuming (focus will be on the long-term legal framework);
- serves the purpose it truly needs to and does not become complex;

¹⁶ <https://emmri.unimib.it/>

¹⁷ <http://ritrain.eu/>

- is flexible so it can align itself to the aims of long-term strategy;
- does not delay the start of the long-term sustainable Operational Phase time limited in its nature;
- aims at building up and keeping momentum;

To that end, the Implementation comprises two major activities:

- running so-called pilot services addressing high-priority user demand as identified during EMPHASIS-Prep mapping activities; these pilots (1) enable to generate and show-case early benefits to the community and thus help building awareness and trust, and (2) help to learn and train pan-European service provision while forming the European community around the service provision approach;
- establishing an interim governance scheme supporting (1) high-level decision making on the future of EMPHASIS, and (2) pilot service provision

To that end, EMPHASIS has established an Interim General Assembly (IGA) ¹⁸as highest governing body during the Implementation Phase which

- discusses and approves high-level strategic decisions to ensure the implementation of EMPHASIS;
- decides upon an appropriate legal form and governance;
- decides upon the financial framework;
- selects the host country for the statutory seat;
- decides upon the pan-European service and human resources;
- decides upon work plan for an effective implementation of EMPHASIS.

In June 2021, eleven countries were member of the IGA, with participation of further countries as member or observer being actively encouraged by ongoing direct communication with interested countries. Members in June 2021 are: Belgium, Estonia, France, Germany, Israel, Italy, Portugal, Serbia, Switzerland, The Netherlands, United Kingdom.

With the establishment of the IGA enabling decision-making on the future of EMPHASIS, an association according to German law (titled “EPP-RI eV”) has been established supporting pilot

¹⁸ <https://emphasis.plant-phenotyping.eu/iga>

service provision. It sets the required legal framework in order to perform all the activities described in the Implementation Work Plan (see pages 26 ff) while having been easy to be set up, enabling lean management, and allowing for flexibility. The association is purely intended to path the way towards Operation until the Operational Phase legal framework “European Research Infrastructure Consortium” (ERIC) could be established.

ERIC as Operational Phase legal framework

Out of five options for the Operational Phase assessed, the “European Research Infrastructure Consortium” has been identified as the most adequate one supporting EMPHASIS service provision in a best possible manner. The majority of the IGA has accordingly approved ERIC as the long-term framework in March 2021 to be established.

Criteria which have been assessed and lead to the decision on ERIC included:

- Membership by institutions from EU/EEA Member States;
- Membership by institutions from non-EU/EEA Member States;
- Membership by EU/EEA and non-EU/EEA governments (ministries) as well as International Organisations (IOs);
- A flexible governance structure suitable for the envisaged structure of the EMPHASIS governance;
- A European dimension, supporting the image of EMPHASIS RI as a pan-European project;
- Full legal capacity recognised in all EU Member States;
- Ability to contract with third parties, employ personnel, own property, open a bank account, etc.;
- The possibility to be present in other Member States, e.g., the establishment of subsidiaries (or similar) in other jurisdictions for hosting the functional units;
- Voting rights, specifically the potential to allow unanimous voting;
- A fast and simple establishment process of the legal entity;
- Any limitations on profit-generating activities;
- A flexible procurement regime and exemption from the EU procurement directives as implemented in national law;
- Exemption from VAT;
- Other privileges and immunities;

- Limited liability regime;
- Initial capital requirements;
- Ability to apply and receive EU grants;
- Possible links and collaboration with other RIs.

To the time of finalisation of that report (June 2021), EMPHASIS has been working towards the respective documentation required to initiate the ERIC-application process with the European Commission.

Further details on the EMPHASIS governance can be found in:

- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D5.1 Scenarios for governance structures,
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D5.2: Rules for the representation of national infrastructures,
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D5.3: Options to form a legal entity,
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D5.4: Governance framework including roles and responsibilities for the implementation phase,
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D5.5: Report on operations for selection of host country for EMPHASIS central hub and potential services,
- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D5.6: Governance and Statutes for the EMPHASIS Operational Phase.

5. Core aspects of cost model

This chapter focuses on cost models relevant for the operation of EMPHASIS. As such it addresses potential cost model of i) the Operational Phase EMPHASIS entity facilitating access to services and resources ii) service provision at the installations or institutional level such as access to phenotyping facilities. The institutions, based on current operational models of ESFRI distributed research infrastructures, will not be part of the EMPHASIS legal entity but provide services based on Service Level Agreements between the EMPHASIS legal entity and the institutions owning the facilities or the national nodes. Clear and transparent cost models are important to implement comparable acceptable accounting rules and for every involved facility and country.

The Operational Phase of EMPHASIS will presumably start 2022/2023, and its cost model will be largely defined by the decision taken by the Interim General Assembly on the financial aspects of EMPHASIS (see also Deliverables D1.5 and D1.6 of EMPHASIS-Prep). In order to support this decision making process, a number of cost model options will be provided to the IGA. In order to facilitate confidential discussion between the IGA members, these cost model options will not be presented publicly as part of this report. However, basic considerations can be found in the following:

Usually, costs of research infrastructures may include payments (cash outflows) or resources that have to be employed (in-kind contribution), depending on the developmental stage of the research infrastructure for the design, preparation, construction or set up, operation, maintenance, upgrade and decommissioning. According to the current business model canvas of EMPHASIS (described in Deliverable D 6.2) EMPHASIS will provide a full range of pan-European services by a Support and Coordination Unit complemented by further Functional Units (Central Services) potentially distributed in different countries. As a distributed infrastructure the EMPHASIS entity will not own any installations but facilitate access and other services. Thus, the cost considerations focus on the operations of the Functional Units (or Central Services).

EMPHASIS would as such coordinate and facilitate access to installation resources and other services at the institutions of member countries of EMPHASIS. The concrete access procedure to the installation and services (and the involved responsibilities and duties) will be based on Service Level Agreements between the EMPHASIS and the interested institutions (or national nodes) hosting the installations/services.

The cost calculations will follow the recommendations and guidelines from the “Guidelines on cost estimation of research infrastructures”¹⁹.

Further details on the EMPHASIS Operational Phase cost model can be found in:

- EMPHASIS-Prep Deliverable D2.7: Operation cost models.

¹⁹ <https://www.esfri.eu/latest-esfri-news/new-study-guidelines-cost-estimation-research-infrastructures-str-esfri>

6. Implementation Work Plan: The road to operation

Background

The Implementation Phase aims at developing a decision-making process within a framework of an Implementation Governance. Members of the EMPHASIS Implementation Governance for the Implementation Phase are signatories to the EMPHASIS Implementation Phase Letter of Intent (LoI). This LoI has no legally binding obligations to the signatories and no commitment of financial contributions towards the operational phase of EMPHASIS. To ensure that the project momentum is maintained and EMPHASIS can move effectively towards operation after EC funding expires in June 2021 (taking into account a 6-month extension of the EMPHASIS-Prep project) signatories to the EMPHASIS LoI are being solicited to support activities during the EMPHASIS Implementation Phase by financial and/or in kind contributions.

These implementation activities will generate an early impact for all EMPHASIS stakeholders in participating countries including facility operators, users from academia and industry, policy makers, funder and allow an effective transition into operation with a full set of services. The goal is to allow cost-effective investment in development and use of required and complementary infrastructure and related services to achieve the objectives of EMPHASIS. The Implementation Phase activities will enhance these developments by:

- Enabling excellent science by utilizing synergies in integrated infrastructures and implementing pan-European harmonised access to a wide range of installations and services (WP 2-7).
- Attracting a diverse and multidisciplinary community, including plant science, agriculture and the food sector towards EMPHASIS service portfolio (WP1);
- Developing and implementing a legal framework that serves EMPHASIS operation in the best possible manner (WP1)
- Providing service level agreements for pan-European harmonised access to field sites for plant phenotyping (WP2, WP4);
- Fostering technological innovation within the plant phenotyping and agricultural sector by the provision of 'development access' to phenotyping facilities to support in-situ evaluation of emerging methods and technologies (WP3);
- Implementing experimental and data standards that will enable data reusability and reduce operating costs (WP4, 5)

- Supporting model-based data analysis to improve phenotyping itself and to enable predictive breeding (WP6), training new generations of experts making use of interdisciplinary technologies, and fostering transfer of knowledge (WP7)

During its first year, the Implementation Phase of EMPHASIS will focus on the decisions concerning pilot services related to the evaluation and operational development and test aiming at services and access, in preparation of the Operational Phase. This involves: (i) implementation of the pilot services conceptualised in the EU-funded Preparatory Phase (EMPHASIS-PREP) provided they are recommended by experts of scientific advisory board of EMPHASIS and approved by the IGA (ii) establishment of new pilots proposed by IGA members and approved by the IGA. The chosen pilots will show benefits for users, meeting demands identified during previous mapping activities, and thus have a key role in working towards further developing the relationships between EMPHASIS and stakeholders. These potential pilot services are detailed further within this document as Implementation Phase Work Packages. Information on tasks and deliverable for each work package are provided as well as (minimum) required resources. The services to be evaluated are:

- WP1: Support and coordination - administration of EMPHASIS Implementation Phase
- WP2: Field - investigate feasibility of standardised and interoperable multi-environment field experiments
- WP3: Innovation - support and drive innovation in plant phenotyping technologies
- WP4: Harmonisation - provide community guidance on experimental and data standards
- WP5: Data management - provide access to FAIR datasets and develop a pan-European Information System
- WP6: Modelling - improve the connectivity between the phenomics and the modelling communities
- WP7: Training and transfer of knowledge

Implementation Phase activities require pan-European efforts in every country that would be supported by coordination activities all over Europe as outlined in all work packages. In the presented scenario these support actions are estimated to raise costs in the amount of 1037.5 k€, complemented by an estimated 1 FTE in each country, beginning January 2021 and running for 12 months (for details see: "Required resources and management). Detailed resources for the implementation of the services (in cash or in kind) will be evaluated after these services are assessed and recommended by a Scientific Advisory Board and approved by the IGA.

For an efficient financial and administrative management an Association as a legal entity for the management of the Implantation Phase has been established. The Association includes

representatives of all countries involved in the IGA, with the IGA as main decision making body for high level strategic aspects. It will allow an open and transparent, financial, administrative and scientific management of the Implementation Phase activities including the evaluation and implementation of the proposed pilot services (for details see “Management”).

Implementation work plan

The work plan provides details on the proposed EMPHASIS Implementation Phase activities with deliverables and estimated costs required to address the proposed activities related to:

- Support and coordination of the development of a legal framework for EMPHASIS operation (WP1)
- Pilot services (WP2-WP7): these activities have been initiated within the Preparatory Phase (EMPHASIS-PREP) and may be continued within the EMPHASIS Implementation Phase provided they are recommended by a Scientific Advisory Board and approved by the IGA. Additional pilot services can be developed and suggested by the partners of the Implementation Phase and will be decided by the IGA after an evaluation similar to that of other services.

Work Package 1: Coordination, Business Case and Legal Framework

Objectives

This work package coordinates all activities to enable a smooth transition towards a sustainable Operational Phase framework. This includes the engagement of different stakeholders from member countries to establish a legal framework, the evaluation and establishment of a cost-funding framework to support service provision (Business Case) and the support of decision making in the Implementation Phase. The work package will establish an Interim Support and Coordination Office (ISCO).

Task 1.1: Development and implementation of a legal framework for the Implementation Phase

- Developing and registering a legal framework for the open and transparent management of the Implementation Phase (see “Management”);
- Support all the activities of the interim legal framework;
- Establish an Advisory Board to support the legal governance of the Implementation Phase and IGA with respect to scientific, administrative activities;
- Coordinating the evaluation of ongoing pilot services and establishment of new services suggested by the IGA partners and approved by the IGA.

Task 1.2: Development and implementation of a legal entity for the Operational Phase.

- Coordinating selection processes for Functional Units as the organizational units bundling a set of services within a specific area such as e.g. services related to access, to quality management, innovation, training etc. (criterial lists, open call, review);
- Providing documentation of rules for Operational Phase legal entity:
 - Legal entity statutes
 - Service level agreement which depend on the final governance.
 - Company policies an an important item in the construction of the infrastructure. (access, data, human resources, innovation)
- Coordinating decision making by IGA according to the IGA Rules of Procedure on strategic business plan options;
- Coordinating selection process for statutory seat country (country where EMPHASIS legal entity is registered);
- Financial and risk management for implementation phase;

Task 1.3: Secure funding for Operational Phase

- Promoting the relevance of plant phenotyping and/or research infrastructures with funders via funders advisory board;
- Coordinating the development of financial support for plant phenotyping infrastructure for the EMPHASIS Operational Phase (e.g. EU infrastructure project following EPPN2020, ERA-NET-like project);
- Promoting the interaction with other ESFRI projects by applications for cluster projects to use synergies between infrastructures;

Task 1.4: Developing the pan-European phenotyping community and user base

- Supporting the development and integration of national plant phenotyping infrastructures and communities; based on the already achieved results of EMPHASIS-PREP
- Co-organising European Plant Phenotyping Symposium 2021 (together with the International Plant Phenotyping Network and EPPN2020 as a key event to bring together stakeholders from academia, industry, policy making, funding from Europe and beyond. The event will be complemented by dedicated workshops, round table discussions, training schools;
- Operating communication activities, with a main focus on supporting pilot services, development of national infrastructures, aiming at further raising awareness with EMPHASIS infrastructure and services and further develop pan-European user base;
- Operating communication activities synergistically with partnering European RIs (within EOSC-Life, CORBEL, ENVRiplus, RI-VIS, EMMRI) to attract neighbouring communities to EMPHASIS services;

Task 1.5. Coordination, Reporting and Controlling

- Preparation of the IGA meetings and documents;

- Coordination of the pilot services and preparation of the service portfolio of the Operational Phase;
- Coordinating the evaluation of progress and reporting of the pilot activities to the IGA;
- Operating the EMPHASIS Implementation Phase according to the statutes laid down for the Implementation Phase;
- Establishing communication and interaction opportunities between stakeholders;
- Establishment processes for coordination, reporting and controlling for the Operational Phase

Deliverables

No.	Deliverable name	Due date (month)	Responsible	Description
D1.1	Establish the legal framework for the Implementation Phase	01.2021	ISCO	Registration of the legal entity after approval by the IGA
D1.2	Reports on progress in the work plan to the IGA	Recurring (05.2021; 10.2021)	ISCO	Report on IGA meetings
D1.3	Selection process for Functional Units, the EMPHASIS service units	04.2021	ISCO	Criteria list, process description, results
D1.4	Selection of Statutory Seat country	06.2021	ISCO	Criteria list, process description, results
D1.5	Draft Statutes and contribution mode	03.2021	ISCO	Draft Statutes
D1.6	Scientific and technical document business model	03.2021	ISCO	First draft of the business model
D.1.7	Cost book	03.2021	ISCO	First draft of the cost book
D.1.8	Company policies	07.2021	ISCO	Draft policies for operating the EMPHASIS organisation
D1.9	Service level agreement	07.2021	ISCO	Draft service level agreements for all infrastructure categories

D1.10	European Plant Phenotyping Conference	10.2021	ISCO	Report on conference
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Work Package 2: Field pilot service

Objectives

EMPHASIS will facilitate standardized and interoperable plant phenotyping in multi-environment field experiments through co-ordinated services. Field phenotyping is highly demanded by the scientific community and regarded as very challenging. In this pilot, first steps will be taken to enable multi-environmental field experiments across field phenotyping infrastructures. The pilot will identify suitable field infrastructures, draft services, level agreements with participating countries including minimal requirements, equipment, logistics, data- and protocol management and access models.

Task 2.1 Identifying suitable field infrastructures, including:

- access models: what sites are available for access;
- available equipment, both for phenotyping and for environmental- and physiological monitoring;
- specific logistics such as agronomic management of qualifying field sites;
- training requirements;

Task 2.2 Drafting service level agreement (SLA) for participating facilities, including:

- defining minimum requirement to qualify for plant phenotyping field sites (in cooperation with the harmonisation and the data pilot);
- minimum requirements for data management (e.g. FAIR principles, open source repository of data, in cooperation with the data pilot);
- quality policies (e.g. cost models, protocol handling, data and statistical design);

Task 2.3 Supporting for researchers involved in multi-environment field trial experiment, including:

- identifying funding opportunities, e.g. ERA-Net like project (link to WP1);
- developing procedures for access calls for field experiments;
- training researchers for e.g. setting up field experiments (Link to WP7);
- establishment of a processes continuing field phenotyping approaches for the Operational Phase

Deliverables

No.	Deliverable name	Due date (month)	Responsible	Description
D2.1	Identifying the suitable field infrastructures	04.2021	Field pilot Coordinator with country support	Database, website.
D2.2	Establishing minimal requirement list	06.2021	Field pilot Coordinator with country support	Criteria list
D2.3	Drafting service level agreement (SLA) for participating facilities	11.2021	Field pilot Coordinator and ISCO	SLA and access models
D2.4	Support for researchers involved in multi-environment field trial experiment	12.2021	Field pilot Coordinator and ISCO	Funding, access mode, training

Work Package 3: Innovation pilot service

Objectives

EMPHASIS builds upon the significant advances in plant phenotyping technology, infrastructure and methods that have taken place across Europe over the last decade. These provide a solid basis for the construction and operation of a pan-European research infrastructure. However, the continuing, rapid developments seen in core technology areas of sensors, robotics and artificial intelligence present both an opportunity and a challenge. Monitoring and exploiting research and development in appropriate areas will allow EMPHASIS to remain at the forefront of plant phenotyping into the future. Constant (re-)development is needed to ensure that EMPHASIS facilities employ the best available technologies and methods, and continue to provide a high quality of service. EMPHASIS facilities represent a valuable testbed for those developing new approaches and, more importantly, confidence in EMPHASIS' internal market will allow public research agencies and SMEs to justify investment in the development of plant phenotyping tools, supporting mission-oriented innovation policy (Mazzucato 2017). For this to occur, EMPHASIS must develop procedures to identify relevant key and common challenges, and processes to coordinate and adopt new methods as they appear.

The aims of the EMPHASIS Innovation Services are therefore:

1. to ensure the long-term sustainable excellence of the infrastructure
2. to support and drive innovation in plant phenotyping technologies, tools and methods by the wider industrial and academic communities.

A key role for EMPHASIS' Innovation Services will also be to act as a broker between infrastructure operators/users and technology developers/suppliers.

Task 3.1. Engage with Key Sectors and Actors.

- Create a register of academic experts in key areas of phenotyping and associated technologies.
- Create a register of industrial contacts and bodies, identifying their areas of technical expertise and product development.
- Establish an innovation board in collaboration with the IGA that will draw on the above registers to evaluate and create and implement innovative tools and methods.

Task 3.2. Innovation services for EMPHASIS infrastructures and users.

- Poll the IGA members and users for i) technical challenges and ii) emerging technologies they require guidance on, produce and distribute briefing papers on those topics
- Make members that registered as experts to provide individual advice on available tools and methods, monitor level of interest and nature of queries.
- Establishment of a processes continuing innovation actions for the Operational Phase

Task 3.3. Innovation services for industrial and academic developers especially with respect to imaging and AI/machine learning. EPPN2020 has demonstrated a mechanism for the provision of 'development access' to phenotyping facilities to support in-situ evaluation of emerging methods.

The development of AI/machine learning based solutions, however, relies more heavily on access to annotated image and sensor data.

- Review annotated image datasets i) currently available for use in developing AI-based phenotyping technology, ii) desired by members of the industrial and academic registers, iii) potentially available with EMPHASIS facilities.
- Create and make available online (e.g. via the Nottingham Annotated Crop Image Database, <https://plantimages.nottingham.ac.uk/>) a sample EMPHASIS annotated image dataset.

Deliverables

No.	Deliverable name	Due date (month)	Responsible	Description
D3.1	Innovation Board	02.2021	Innovation pilot coordinator with country support	Membership and Terms of Reference of Innovation Board
D3.2	Technology Briefing Paper	04.2021	Innovation pilot coordinator with country and Innovation Board support	Report on current status and potential value to the phenotyping community of the agreed technology
D3.3	Challenge Briefing Paper	08.2021	Innovation pilot coordinator with country and Innovation Board support	Report on current opportunities to and roadblocks preventing achievement of the agreed challenge
D3.4	First EMPHASIS Innovation Dataset	12.2021	Innovation pilot coordinator with country and Innovation Board support	Annotated dataset, freely available in a standard format and desired by the AI development community
D3.5.	Engagement Report	12.2021	Innovation pilot coordinator with Innovation Board support	Summary of interactions between EMPHASIS operators/users, industrial and academic expert registers

Work Package 4: Harmonisation pilot service

Objectives

The harmonisation pilot will evaluate how to establish EMPHASIS as a central point of information on how to perform plant phenotyping experiments according to state of the art procedures. The aim is to develop and communicate with the plant phenotyping community on best practices (Good Phenotyping Practice). This will be a prerequisite to allow experimental reproducibility between infrastructures and reusability of the obtained data (e.g. by defining standards. Minimum requirements for plant phenotyping experiments under controlled and field conditions will be defined and guidelines on use and calibration of sensors will be communicated.

Task 4.1 Community exchange on harmonisation

- Organize workshops and round table discussions with operators of plant phenotyping facilities and users on Good Phenotyping Practice in all infrastructure categories:
 - i) controlled environment,
 - ii) intense field,
 - iii) lean field (Link to WP2),
 - iv) data and computational services (Link to WP5),
 - v) modelling (Link to WP6)

Task 4.2 Requirements for Good Phenotyping Practice

- Evaluate and define experimental procedures required to enable comparability of experiments with focus on experimental design and analysis for single and multiple installation experiments, environmental monitoring, sensor calibration and application etc. (here we will use preliminary work from EPPN/EPPN2020 and extend it to EMPHASIS members)
- Map, evaluate and extend existing repositories hosting plant phenotyping protocols and their accessibility for the user community;
- Develop an EMPHASIS repository integrating information from existing repositories as well as new protocols and quality measures required for Good Phenotyping practice in plant phenotyping.
- Establishment of a processes continuing quality assurance for the Operational Phase

Deliverables

No.	Deliverable name	Due date (month)	Responsible	Description
D4.1	Criteria for experimental procedures	05.2021	Harmonisation pilot coordinator	List of experimental procedures
D4.2	Good phenotyping practice repositories	05.2021	Harmonisation pilot coordinator	Establish a repository for protocols
D4.3	Community exchange on harmonisation	09.2021	Harmonisation pilot coordinator	Multiple workshops and round table discussions

Work Package 5: Data management pilot service

Objectives

The objective of this pilot is to implement FAIR principles (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable) to ensure that the datasets that are and will be collected in EMPHASIS installations are available to a large community of plant scientists. Such 'open science' approaches are increasingly required by most journals, on national and European level. Three levels of data management are defined to graduate the efforts needed in order to have the best practices:

Level 1: Data Identification and organization ('Reusable')

- Improve the quality of data: identifiers, spatial positions, events and variables, metadata.

Level 2: Local information system for environmental and phenotypic datasets

- Improve the quality of access to the data using information systems.

Level 3: A multi local information system facilitating meta-analyses

- Multi-site access through EMPHASIS-Layer.

Task 5.1: Providing support to reach level 1-2 compliance

- Helping partners to reach minimum requirements guidelines level 1&2 based on the implementation of those requirements in EPPN2020
- Developing information systems that can handle datasets obtained in both controlled condition and field conditions, with common ontologies of events, objects and traits
- Ensuring the compatibility of information systems deployed in different nodes (with WP communication)
- Organizing workshops and training to support the implementation of level 1&2 in EMPHASIS IGA countries (Link to WP7)
- Help local infrastructures to implement information systems, in particular with ontologies of objects, events and traits not considered in other local information systems, with the help of selected European SMEs

Task 5.2: Implementing the EMPHASIS-layer

- Establishing the strategy for an integrated European Phenotypic Information System including common ontologies and Web Services across platforms in controlled and field conditions (EMPHASIS-Layer)
- Providing a "use case" to demonstrate the use of Emphasis-Layer, including three local infrastructures connected to the layer from different countries.

- Implement further local infrastructures into the EMPHASIS-Layer by providing support and consulting

Task 5.3: Establish Data Management Policy for EMPHASIS

- Develop and implement rules on data property, sharing and right of the first use, including necessary metadata for FAIR sharing in accordance to the EU policy of open data.
- Establishment of a processes for data management towards the Operational Phase

Deliverables

No.	Deliverable name	Due date	Responsible	Description
D5.1	EMPHASIS-Layer proof of concept	02.2021	Data pilot coordinator	Report on the operational EMPHASIS Layer
D5.2	Minimum requirements guidelines for Level 1&2	05.2021	Data pilot coordinator	Set of guidelines required for the implementation of Level 1&2
D5.3	Workshops and training	07.2021	Data pilot coordinator	Report on workshops and trainings on the implementation of Level 1&2&3
D5.4	Data Management Policy	09.2021	Data pilot coordinator	Data management policy from EMPHASIS
D5.5	EMPHASIS-Layer implementation	12.2021	Data pilot coordinator	EMPHASIS layer implemented in multiple local infrastructures

Work Package 6. Modelling pilot service

Objectives

The plant phenotyping space is too immense to observe all aspects of the phenotype in all combinations of genotypes by growth stage by environmental conditions. Mathematical modelling offers many opportunities to enlarge the phenotypic space of phenotyping experiments through the

computation of novel traits that are not directly accessible to available sensors. In addition, modelling also helps capturing the essence of observed phenomics data to predict integrated (e.g. yield) or functional traits (e.g. plant root system architecture) for new genotypes across a wide range of target environments or management practices. Leveraging the power of mathematical modelling in plant phenotyping depends on our ability to feed phenome data into structural plant models (SPMs), functional-structural plant models (FSPMs) and process-based crop simulation models (CSMs). This goes beyond the data management challenge, as it depends on the ability of the plant phenotyping community to design experiments and platforms that yield suitable data for modelling, and reversely. It is one of the objectives of EMPHASIS to improve the connectivity between the phenomics and the modelling communities.

Task 6.1: Get and keep the plant phenomics community aware of model applications

- Maintain and update the online portal (quantitative-plant.org, developed by EMPHASIS-PREP) referencing plant and crop simulation models.
- Promote the interest to modelling by advertising this website within the phenomics community.

Task 6.2: Help users, platform managers and model developers to design model-based data analysis pipelines to improve phenotypic output

- Develop an interactive web companion to explore possible connections between phenotyping platforms outputs, models inputs and models outputs. This online tool would serve different purpose:
 - identify possible model outputs (e.g. yield, root system architecture...) for a given phenotype dataset.
 - reversely, identify the phenotyping platforms that are suitable to feed data into a given model.
 - allow platform managers to adjust their output capabilities to support modelling, and allow model developers to adjust their input to available phenotype variables.
 - show a clear view of platforms outputs, models inputs and models outputs and allow users to design a data analysis graph linking phenotypic data and models to get to their variables of interest.

Task 6.3: Simplify the translation from phenomics datasets to model inputs

- Map existing initiatives from modelling communities (e.g. ICASA) and identify clusters of model parameters that are likely to have synonyms or like equivalents in phenotyping outputs.

- Use Implementation Phase partners to build a list of variables from phenotyping platforms and create clusters of variables that can be aligned on the clusters of model inputs.
- Express these informations in a hierarchical ontologies allowing to create graphs of output-to-input at different granularities. Create a graph linking the different clusters and identify simple models (based on simple function, regression, expert knowledge) that can be used to translate similar variables from both sides. This will be feedback into Task 6.2.

Deliverables

No.	Deliverable name	Due date (month)	Responsible	Description
D6.1	Inform the plant phenomics community about the model applications	12. 2021	Modelling pilot Coordinator	Report on use of the plant and crop models
D6.2	Support developers to design model-based data analysis pipelines to improve phenotypic output	06. 2021	Modelling pilot Coordinator	Demonstrate an interactive web companion to find possible connections between phenotyping platforms outputs, models' inputs and models' outputs
D6.3	Simplify the translation from phenomics datasets to model inputs	09. 2021	Modelling pilot Coordinator	Demonstrate that appropriate ontologies can support aligning phenotypic variables, model parameters and model outputs

Work Package 7: Training pilot service (incl transfer of knowledge)

Objectives

The training pilot, to be tested during the implementation phase, is intended to implement innovative methods of training in plant phenotyping, with emphasis on technological methods allowing remote transfer of knowledge during the COVID-19 emergency and post-emergency.

EMPHASIS will coordinate and support the user training activities in plant phenotyping according to the needs and expectations of the plant phenotyping community, already identified by EMPHASIS-PREP and further developed by pilots 2-6 of EMPHASIS implementation phase. The Training pilot aims at performing as a guidance about what competencies are required in plant phenotyping in order to coordinate, design and execute training courses for different target groups, facilitating access to training material and supplying updated training and transfer of knowledge offer, especially aimed at remote, on-line access. The Training WP would closely interact with other WPs to specifically address the training needs that may be required by specific services.

The training pilot service will also promote and stimulate the collaboration with other training institutions such as universities, research centers, ESFRI projects, end-users, stakeholders, and the civil society.

Task 7.1 Coordination of EMPHASIS training activities on plant phenotyping:

- Identify specialized training topics and ToK activities [with the support of the other WPs (pilot services)] for already identified training target groups (researchers, technology developers, modelers,..)
- Develop an EMPHASIS training network among IGA participants
- Stimulate collaboration and communication with universities research centres, other ESFRI projects and clusters regarding training activities
- Support EMPHASIS national nodes in organizing training initiatives and coordination for practical implementation of EMPHASIS conference.
- Identify and propose funding opportunities aimed at supporting training and ToK activities (e.g. ITN, ETN);

Task 7.2 Planning of training activities

- Plan, propose and implement training activities along the implementation phase, including activities that may allow continuous and efficient transfer of knowledge under limitation of traveling because of COVID-19 emergency and post-emergency.
- Identify quality criteria and policies for high quality training activities (minimum requirement, training KPIs,..)
- Develop a trainer/trainee register
- Develop, implement and maintain an online course catalogue and quality indicators
- Disseminate the EMPHASIS training offer with the support of WP1

Deliverables

No.	Deliverable name	Due date (month)	Responsible	Description
D7.1	Identification of training topics per different target groups	12.2020	Training pilot Coordinator with other WP support	Mapping
D7.2	Definition of quality criteria and policies for training activities	02.2021	Training pilot Coordinator with country support	Criteria list
D7.3	Plan of training activities (b.a.u. or under sanitary contingency)	02.2021	Training pilot Coordinator and ISCO	Report on proposed training activities
D 7.4	Analysis of the EMPHASIS training activities offered in the implementation phase.	12.2021	Training pilot Coordinator and ISCO	Assessment report

Management and required resources

Financial contribution model

The financial contributions required to cover the cost related to EMPHASIS implementation (roughly 1 Mio €) are provided by the IGA member countries both via cash and in-kind contributions. All the personal costs related to the performance of the tasks described in the Implementation phase Work Plan are covered in-kind. Other direct costs are covered in cash by all IGA members based on a contribution model accounting for 60 % equal share and 40 % GDP based contribution. These other direct costs may include any external paid advice (legal, socio-economic study etc.), maintenance of websites, servers, databases, travelling etc.

Interim legal framework supporting Implementation Phase activities

An Association (German e.V.) has been established as a legal entity for the Implementation Phase enabling an open, transparent and effective management of the financial and administrative processes of the Implementation Phase. The Association includes members from plant phenotyping centres in Europe. It provides a supporting framework for management and accounting of financial contributions for the Implementation Phase of EMPHASIS with the IGA decision making body about the resources. It enables high-level decision making by the IGA related to all aspects of the EMPHASIS Implementation Work Plan.

Key benefits of the association:

- The formal step to found and register an association takes approximately 3-4 weeks.
- The association includes a simple legal framework that allows an open and transparent governance and decision making process related to financial and administrative management of the Implementation Phase resources.
- High level of flexibility: The association enables well needed flexibility required for also for the financial management of the Implementation Phase based on legally binding rules.
- The IGA ONLY decides about the use of resources managed by the association.
- Supporting open character of EMPHASIS: It would enable openness towards further plant phenotyping institutions in current or future IGA countries joining EMPHASIS in the course of the implementation phase. It thus supports a dynamic evolution of service provision and progress towards a truly pan-European scope
- Easy: The association can be established easily, cost effectively with simple rules (as already practiced with IPPN).
- Existing legal support: There is established support by legal, administrative and financial experts assisting IPPN e.V with extensive experience in management of international associations.
- Practical experience: Many plant phenotyping institutions in Europe have already practical experience with this legal framework through IPPN e.V.
- Key features, with further features given in the respective draft of the statutes of the Association, are:

- The Association represents a supporting framework for the IGA and activities related to the implementation, but not the operation of EMPHASIS. The Operational Phase will need another legal framework meeting more adequately the requirements of this Phase.
- The members of the Association will be the scientific institutions with key activities on plant phenotyping.

The IGA is the main decision making body on all high-level strategic options related to EMPHASIS implementation and operation.

Risk management and contingency plan

The Interim General Assembly (IGA) is the key decision-making body based on the Rules of Procedure. All activities related to all steps undertaken in the EMPHASIS Implementation Phase as described in the work plan will be reported to the IGA that will be supported by the Interim Coordination and Support Office. The WP coordinators will report on the activities in the respective Work Packages and oversee all potential risks that may hamper timely and smooth progress of implementation activities. The IGA will be regularly updated on potential risks as part of the IGE meeting preparatory documents (deliverable D1.1).

Risk assessment and contingency measures with regard to Covid19-related limitations

In order to assess potential risks on the progress of EMPHASIS implementation with regard to the impact of Covid-19, all major activities have been evaluated regarding potential impacts considering three potential scenarios:

- Scenario 1: Pandemic is under control but a level of social distancing continues in advance of medical developments. (We are not envisaging any early scenario in which business returns to 'normal').
- Scenario 2: Pandemic is partially controlled. We move in and out of 'lock-down'. Social distancing measures continue, including some travel restrictions
- Scenario 3: Pandemic is not controlled. Increasing number of countries in 'lock-down' and severe travel restrictions; very little face to face provision.

Scenario 1 is assumed to be the one with the highest probability, and scenario 3 the least probable one. The results clearly show that for the scenarios 1 and 2, the implementation activities

can be realised in the envisaged timeframe, based on specific adaptations. Only for scenario 3 (pandemic is not controlled), stronger impacts could result in delays or cancellations of single activities.

Annex 1: Check list

Deliverable Check list (to be checked by the “Deliverable leader”)

	Check list	Comments
Before	I have checked the due date and have planned completion in due time	<i>Please inform Management Team of any foreseen delays</i>
	The title corresponds to the title in the DOW	<i>If not please inform the Management Team with justification</i>
	The dissemination level corresponds to that indicated in the DOW	
	The contributors (authors) correspond to those indicated in the DOW	
	The Table of Contents has been validated with the Activity Leader	<i>Please validate the Table of Content with your Activity Leader before drafting the deliverable</i>
	I am using the EMPHASIS deliverable template (title page, styles etc.)	<i>Available in “New EMPHASIS Logo, Templates, CI” on the collaborative workspace</i>
<i>The draft is ready</i>		
After	I have written a good summary at the beginning of the Deliverable	<i>A 1-2 pages max. summary is mandatory (not formal but really informative on the content of the Deliverable)</i>
	The deliverable has been reviewed by all contributors (authors)	<i>Make sure all contributors have reviewed and approved the final version of the deliverable. You should leave sufficient time for this validation.</i>
	I have done a spell check and verified the English	
	I have sent the final version to the WP Leader and to the Project coordinator (cc to the project manager) for approval	<i>Send the final draft to your WPLLeader and the coordinator with cc to the project manager on the 1st day of the due month and leave 2 weeks for feedback. Inform the reviewer of the changes (if any) you have made to address their comments. Once validated by the 2 reviewers and the coordinator, send the final version to the Project Manager who will then submit it to the EC.</i>